

Integrating Traditional Diagnostics Methods Through Neutrosophic Set Based Cancer Analysis Using Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract: This paper introduces a novel approach for utilizing Neutrosophic Sets through machine learning to enhance classification accuracy by incorporating truth, falsity, and indeterminacy in decision-making. Traditional cancer cell classification models struggle to handle indeterminate cases effectively. A Neutrosophic Confusion Matrix (NCM) is developed to extend conventional performance evaluation metrics, considering the probability distribution of positive, negative, and neutral classifications. This framework enables a more comprehensive assessment of classification reliability, particularly in ambiguous cases where traditional machine-learning models exhibit limitations. The proposed approach for classification uses two significant imagery features: texture contrast and color saturation as well as neutrosophic sets that can effectively differentiate between benign, malignant, and healthy skin lesions through Machine Learning concepts. Through empirical validation of medical datasets, this work establishes Neutrosophic based classification as a powerful tool for improving the accuracy and robustness of cancer diagnosis.

Keywords: Neutrosophic sets; machine learning; neutrosophic confusion matrix; image processing

1. Introduction

Machine Learning has established significant efficiency in determining the existence of cancer cells by evaluating factors and identifying the key components for a precise diagnosis across several models [8]. One of the main causes of death globally, cancer is typified by unchecked cell development that has the potential to spread to other bodily parts. The progression of cancer is typically categorized into stages, ranging from early-stage (localized) to advanced-

stage(metastasized) [1]. Tumor classification is essential for guiding treatment decisions. Malignant lesions are carcinogenic and have the ability to spread to neighboring tissues, whereas benign lesions are usually non-cancerous and do not spread.

Traditional diagnostic methods include biopsy and histopathological analysis, but advancements in medical imaging have allowed for non-invasive techniques to aid in lesion classification. These techniques analyses features from medical images, such as texture and color, to differentiate between benign and malignant growths.

In the context of lesion classification, it is used to find the specific class (benign or malignant) based on extracted image features like texture contrast and color saturation by Machine Learning concepts [9]. This paper presents a methodology for cancer lesion classification using Neutrosophic Sets [6], focusing on two key features: texture contrast and color saturation. This non-invasive, feature-based approach offers a standard foundation for supporting early diagnosis and accurate tumor classification. As a result, conventional image analysis techniques suffer from these image complexity issues and are likely to produce inaccurate results.

1.1 Literature Review

Abdulbaqi et al.[1] investigated the function of neutrosophic logic in the field of medical image processing in an effort to address these issues more effectively. Optimizing noise reduction, picture segmentation, feature extraction, and classification through the unique capabilities of neutrosophic logic aimed at managing uncertainty and indeterminacy were the primary goals of the project. The main goal of the study [2] was to minimize MSE while determining the best accurate estimations for the unknown population mean value. The aim of the proposed work is evaluating the benefits of Neutrosophic Graph Cut-based Segmentation (NGCS) over pre-processed cervical. Devi et al. [3] introduced NGCS-based segmentation which aims to increase classification accuracy and to analyze the context of cervical smear pictures. Das et al. [4] introduced the concept of Neutrosophic Fuzzy Set (NFS) by combining FS [5] and NS [6], which leads to some new ideas. Some real-life problems are difficult for NFS to handle because of the nonstandard interval of neutrosophic components. El-Shorbagy et al. [7] and Siri et al. [8] investigated that in the past ten years, neutrosophic sets have been employed to improve medical imaging. Information indeterminacy and uncertainty can be overcome using neutrophilic sets. Farag et al. [9] integrated bioinformatics algorithms with neutrosophic theory and developed a neutrosophic inference model for bioinformatics. NFS [4] finds it challenging to address some real-life issues Information indeterminacy and uncertainty can be overcome using neutrosophic sets [6].

Okuboyejo and Olugbara [10] emphasized the primary medical image processing techniques that can be created with the NS, such as segmentation, clustering, classification, thresholding, and de-noising. In order to include NS [6] into each activity, general algorithms were suggested. In order to classify a malignant lesion, Singh et al. [11] suggested a computer-aided diagnosis system in which the obtained image is mainly pre-processed utilizing innovative techniques. After removing digital artefacts like blood vessels and hair follicles, the image is improved using a revolutionary technique

called histogram equalization. Bharathi and Jayalalitha [12] introduced neutrosophic fractals which is the combination of neutrosophic logics and fractal geometry. Bharathi and Jayalalitha [12] proved some theorems and examples for demonstrating self-similarity. The new way of approaching on fractal geometry improves the representation of uncertainty, indeterminacy and falsity in neutrosophic logic. Ananthkumar et al. [13] investigated determinant theory for quadri-partitioned neutrosophic fuzzy matrices and grounded an algorithm to address decision making problems. Ananthkumar et al. [14, 15] focused advanced Neutrosophic Fuzzy Matrix (NFM) theory, and generalized minimum norm g -inverse, least square g -inverse etc., for solving systems of neutrosophic fuzzy linear equations. Ananthkumar et al. [16,17] defined secondary k -RS NFMs that were explained about classical symmetry to neutrosophic environments. Their studies [16, 17] enhanced tool for solving neutrosophic linear systems through generalized inverses.

1.2 Research gap

By using statistical patterns from pixel intensity, texture, and form variables, traditional machine learning algorithms, such as Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE), have shown encouraging results in the categorization of skin lesions. Nevertheless, these techniques frequently presume that the data is entirely accurate, clear, and noise-free, which is rarely the case in actual clinical images. Even though MLE is statistically robust, it is unable to deal with the ambiguity, indeterminacy, and inconsistency that are present in medical pictures, particularly in low-contrast or early-stage lesions where it is difficult to distinguish between healthy and malignant tissues. Conversely, Neutrosophic Sets (NSs) [6], which have three membership degrees—Truth (T), Indeterminacy (I), and Falsity (F)—offer a strong mathematical foundation for modelling and processing imprecise, indeterminate, and inconsistent data. However, there is still a lack of research on the application of neutrosophic theory to the categorisation of skin cancer, particularly when combined with machine learning algorithms. Although probabilistic approaches like fuzzy logic have been used in previous publications, they fall short in capturing the dynamic uncertainty structure provided by neutrosophy. The lacks of hybrid models that combine the statistical underpinnings of MLE with the uncertainty modelling capabilities of Neutrosophic Sets [6] for more robust, interpretable, and reliable skin cancer diagnosis which results are substantial research gap. In this article, we explore the algorithm for finding the metrics using NSs [6].

Rest of the article is organized as follows: Section 2 provides preliminaries. Section 3 presents the description about the dataset. Section 4 provides the various details such as methodologies, Extraction methods and Classification process by Machine learning tool, coding CNN with MLE classification. Section 5 provides Evaluation, Integrating Neutrosophic metric and confusion matrix. Section 6 provides final assessment, Analysis, and results. Section 7 concludes paper by stating the future scope of research.

2. Preliminaries

2.1 Neutrosophic Sets

In the late 1990s, Florentin Smarandache developed a mathematical framework known as a NS [18]. Details of the development of NSs and their extensions and applications were depicted in the studies [19-28]. The application of neutrosophic sets in classifying benign, malignant, and healthy individuals using Machine Learning concepts involves leveraging the flexibility and uncertainty-handling capabilities of neutrosophic logic [29].

2.2 Understanding Neutrosophic Sets

Single valued NS was grounded by Wang et al. [30] in 2010 by extending fuzzy sets by incorporating three membership functions: Truth (T): Truth in the set, Indeterminacy (I): Level of indeterminacy or uncertainty, Falsity (F): Degree of falsity. These values are typically represented in the interval [0,1], allowing representation of uncertainty compared to traditional approaches.

3. Dataset Description & Experimental Context

Objective: Classify individuals into three categories: benign, malignant, and healthy.

Features: Use medical data (e.g., imaging results, biomarkers, patient history) as input features.

Challenges: Handle uncertain or incomplete data effectively, as well as overlap between categories.

Dataset : ISIC skin cancer dataset

Classes : Benign, Malignant, Indeterminate

Models:

1. CNN+Softmax (Traditional Classification)
2. CNN+Neutrosophic Logic Classifier

Metrics per class: Precision, Recall, F1-score

Overall : Accuracy

Define Neutrosophic set using MLE

Convert input features into neutrosophic sets with (T,I,F) memberships. Given a dataset with observations that can be classified into Malignant (Truth), Benign (Indeterminacy), and Healthy (Falsity), Let us assume:

- Each observation has an associated probability for T, I, F .
- These probabilities follow a Multinomial distribution.
- $X = \{(T_i, I_i, F_i)\}$ be a dataset of n independent observations.
- Each observation (T_i, I_i, F_i) represents the membership values for an instance.

The **Maximum likelihood function** for all observations is:

$$L(\theta) = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} P(X_i / \theta) = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} P\left(\frac{(T_i, I_i, F_i)}{\theta}\right)$$

where $P(X_i / \theta)$ incorporates the neutrosophic memberships.

3.1 Parameter Estimation

The parameters might define thresholds or distributions for the neutrosophic memberships in each class. Classification: Assign individuals to the category with the highest likelihood, considering the neutrosophic memberships. Benefits of the Approach: Handles Uncertainty: Neutrosophic sets explicitly model the uncertainty and ambiguity in medical data. Improved Classification: Incorporating uncertainty into the likelihood estimation can lead to more robust classification, especially in borderline or ambiguous cases. Adaptable Framework: This method can be adapted to various types of medical data and conditions.

3.2 Input data

The ISIC is an archive which is maintained by International Skin Imaging Collaboration. It is used to collect the dermoscopic images of skin lesions. The study utilizes a dataset from the ISIC, comprising dermoscopic images of two categories of skin cancer: benign and malignant lesions [33]. It serves for ISIC challenges, which is based on machine learning. It is focused on skin lesion analysis and segmentation. Few sample images are taken from the dataset of ISIC which is shown in the below figure 1 and 2. Figure 1 shows that the benign stage cancer cells and Figure 2 shows that the malignant stage cancer cells. Here ISIC 2019 challenge dataset contains images and metadata for multi-class skin lesion classification.

MEL,SCC: Melanoma (Malignant)

NV, BKL, DF : Melanocytic nevus (Benign)

BCC: Basal cell carcinoma (Malignant)

AKIEC, VASC : Indeterminate

The ISIC Achieve has an API. It is bit complex and requires login tokens and rare limits. It is easiest way to use the Kaggle version of the ISIC dataset.

Load ISIC from Kaggle

1. Go to Kaggle>Account> create API Token
2. Pip install kaggle
3. Mkdir ~/.kaggle
4. Cp/path/to.kaggle.json ~/.kaggle/kaggle.json
5. Chmod 600 ~/.kaggle/kaggle.json

Download Dataset

1. Kaggle datasets download kmader/skin-cancer-mnist-ham10000
unzip skin-cancer-mnist-ham10000.zip -d isic_data

Figure 1: Benign Cancer Cells taken from ISIC [33]

Figure 2: Malignant Cancer Cells taken from ISIC [33]

4. Methodologies

4.1 Pre-processing

In numerous ways, the image acquisition process ought to be non-uniform. As a result, the major goal of the preprocessing stage is to improve image attributes like quality, sharpness, and so on by removing or minimizing undesired image or background elements. Grayscale conversion, image enhancement, and noise removal are the critical phases in pre-processing. All photos in this suggested system are first transformed to grayscale. The image is then enhanced, and noise is removed using a Gaussian filter and a median filter. Use a dull razor with a filter to remove unwanted follicles from skin lesions. The purpose of enhanced images is to improve an image's quality by improving its visibility. Most skin lesions are made up of follicles, making accurate classification difficult. The blunt blade method can thus be used to eliminate undesirable hairs from an image.

The DullRazor approach [31] primarily accomplishes the following tasks: a) Using grayscale morphological techniques, locate the position of hairs in the lesion. b) Subsequently detecting the exact place of the hair pixel, determine if the shape is thin or long, and then replace the follicle pixel with bilinear interpolation. Ultimately, the replacement follicle pixels are smoothed utilizing an adaptive median filter. Gaussian filters are employed to blur photos and eliminate superfluous skin lesion features. These are linearly smoothed low-pass filters and use a two-dimensional convolution operator with Gaussian weights.

4.2 Extraction

An essential phase in the classification process is feature extraction, which turns unstructured data into useful attributes that greatly improve the efficiency of detection and classification algorithms. The feature extraction methods used are described in this part, with an emphasis on colour saturation and texture contrast obtained from dermoscopic images.

4.2.1 Texture Contrast Extraction: Determining the image's texture contrast is the initial step in feature extraction. This property is essential for differentiating distinct textures in photographs, especially in medical imaging to detect different kinds of skin lesions. The roughness of the texture

can be measured by examining the intensity contrast between adjacent pixels, which helps distinguish between benign and malignant tumours.

4.2.2 Colour Saturation Extraction:

Determining the image's average colour saturation is the second component of feature extraction. This characteristic is crucial for comprehending the hues' intensity and vibrancy, which can help differentiate between various lesion types. We can improve the categorisation process by learning more about the colour traits linked to particular skin disorders by evaluating the saturation levels in the image.

4.3 In a machine learning pipeline for skin lesion classification Process

A statistical method that makes use of the extracted features—texture contrast and colour saturation—is used to classify the photos. By using predetermined criteria for benign and malignant lesions, this approach makes it possible to identify the kind of lesion based on the estimated probabilities of each classification.

4.3.1 Definition of Parameters

Two sets of parameters are established: one for malignant lesions and another for benign lesions. The contrast and saturation feature mean and variance values are included in each set. These parameters reflect the statistical features of each type of lesion and are obtained from a training dataset.

4.3.2. Likelihood Calculation: The Gaussian probability density function is used to determine the probability of seeing the extracted contrast and saturation features for each categorisation (malignant and benign). The mean and variance of the characteristics for both types of lesions are taken into account in this computation. The retrieved contrast and saturation values are compared to their respective means and variances to calculate the probability of benign lesions. The same process is used to determine the likelihood of malignant lesions.

4.3.3 Likelihood Comparison

Following the computation of the likelihoods for the two classes, a comparison is conducted. We compare the computed likelihoods and assign the class corresponding to the higher one. The image is categorised as "Malignant" if the probability of the malignant class is greater than that of the benign class. A higher benign likelihood, on the other hand, results in the image being labelled "Benign."

4.3. 4 Result and Conclusion

The performance of the classification model was evaluated using two sets of parameters derived from the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) approach. Each parameter set consists of mean and variance values for texture contrast and color saturation, providing insight into the statistical distributions of features associated with benign and malignant lesions.

4.3.5 Coding: CNN with MLE for Skin Cancer Classification

1. Import tensorflow as tf
2. From tensorflow.keras.models import sequential
3. From tensorflow.keras.layers import conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense, Dropout
4. From tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
5. From tensorflow.keras.optimizers import Adam

```
6. #set image size and batch size
7. Img_height, img_width=224,224
8. Batch size =32
9. Num_classes =3
10. #Load dataset (replace with correct path)
11. Train_datagen=ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1/255,validation_split=0.2)
12. Train_generator=train_datagen.flow_from_directory(
13. 'skin_cancer_dataset/'
14. Target_size=(img_height, img_width),
15. Batch_size=batch_size,
16. Class_mode='categorical',
17. Subset='training'
18. )
19. Val_generator = train_datagen.flow_from_directory(
20. 'skin_cancer_dataset/'
21. Target_size=(img_height, img_width),
22. Batch_size=batch_size,
23. Class_mode='categorical',
24. Subset='validation'
25. )
26. #Build CNN model
27. Model=sequential([
28. Conv2D(32, (3,3) activation='relu', input_shape=(img_height,img_width,3))
29. MaxPooling2D(2,2),
30. Flatten(),
31. Dense(128,activation='relu'),
32. Dropout(0.5),
33. Dense(num_classes, activation='softmax')
34. ])
35. #compile with categorical_crossentropy(MLE for classification)
36. Model.compile(optimizer=Adam(learning_rate=0.0001),
37. Loss='categorical_crossentropy'
38. Metrics=['accuracy']
```

```

39. Model.fit(train_generator,
40. Validation_data = val_generator,
41. Epochs=15)

```

5. Model Evaluation

It is essential to evaluate the model's performance on a different test set that was never used during the training or validation stages after it has been trained. This evaluation makes it more likely that the model will perform well on actual data and generalize successfully. This section outlines the procedures and techniques used to assess the skin classification model's performance.

5.1 Test Set Evaluation

A test set, which is made up of data that hasn't been utilized for training or validation, is used to evaluate the model. The test set is a crucial part of evaluating the model's capacity for generalization. The trained model is fed with images from the test set, and predictions are made. The main goal is to determine how accurately the model can classify skin images into the three categories: **benign**, **malignant**, and **indeterminate** [32]. Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1-Score has been calculated for Parameter Set 1 (Figure 4) and 2 (Figure 5) which is set of cancer cells taken from ISIC. It is shown in Figure 3, 4 & 5. The study [32] combined the strength of machine learning and neutrosophic theory to enhance the accuracy of breast cancer diagnosis. It uses four prominent machine learning models enhances the predictive ability of the proposed model.

Lesion Type	Feature	Mean	Variance
1st Parameter Set			
Benign	Contrast	18.33	1121.1
	Saturation	36.2	224.23
Malignant	Contrast	154.93	23452.28
	Saturation	113.90	411.5
2nd Parameter Set			
Benign	Contrast	37.3108	1281.097
	Saturation	57.05223	235.2318
Malignant	Contrast	178.9194	27472.2800
	Saturation	116.8988	412.0197

Figure 3: Output consolidation of Traditional Evaluation

Figure 4: Parameter Set 1 - Evaluation

Figure 5: Parameter Set 2 - Evaluation

5.2 Neutrosophic Metric Integration & Confusion Matrix

3 × 3 neutrosophic confusion matrix, where each cell contains a triplet (Positive, Negative, Neutral) representing transition probabilities. This extends the traditional confusion matrix by incorporating indeterminacy and uncertainty. The structured neutrosophic confusion matrix is evaluating cancer cell classification [29].

5.2.1 Performance Metrics

The neutrosophic confusion matrix yields a number of important metrics that are used to assess the model's classification performance is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Neutrosophic Confusion Matrix Structure

ACTUAL/PREDICTED	POSITIVE(P)	NEGATIVE(N)	NEUTRAL (Ne)
True (T)	P1 (TP)	N1 (FN)	Ne1 (FN)
Falsity (F)	P2 (FP)	N2 (TN)	Ne2 (FP)
Indeterminate (I)	P3 (FP)	N3 (FN)	Ne3 (TP)

From the neutrosophic confusion matrix, we can calculate the following performance metrics.

Explanation of Terms

1. **P1 (True Positive for True class)**
 - The number of **True** instances correctly classified as **Positive**.
2. **P2 (False Positive for False class)**
 - The number of **False** instances incorrectly classified as **Positive**.
3. **P3 (False Positive for Indeterminate class)**
 - The number of **Indeterminate** instances incorrectly classified as **Positive**.

4. **N1 (False Negative for True class)**

- The number of **True** instances incorrectly classified as **Negative**.

5. **N2 (True Negative for False class)**

- The number of **False** instances correctly classified as **Negative**.

6. **N3 (False Negative for Indeterminate class)**

- The number of **Indeterminate** instances incorrectly classified as **Negative**.

7. **Ne1 (False Negative for True class as Neutral)**

- The number of **True** instances incorrectly classified as **Neutral**.

8. **Ne2 (False Positive for False class as Neutral)**

- The number of **False** instances incorrectly classified as **Neutral**.

9. **Ne3 (True Positive for Indeterminate class)**

- The number of **Indeterminate** instances correctly classified as **Neutral**.

5.2.2 Accuracy

The overall indicator of the model's soundness is accuracy. It is computed as the proportion of accurate predictions to all predictions. In a **Neutrosophic Confusion Matrix**, each prediction has three degrees:

- **T** → Degree of Truth (certainty in classification)
- **I** → Degree of Indeterminacy (uncertainty or partial correctness)
- **F** → Degree of Falsity (wrong classification)
- Neutrosophic Accuracy = $\frac{\sum(T_i + 0.5 I_i)}{N}$ (1)

where:

- T_i = Truth membership for correctly classified instances.
- I_i = Indeterminacy (uncertain or partially correct classifications).
- F_i = Falsity (incorrect classifications, not used in accuracy).
- N = Total number of samples.
- The **0.5 weight on I** represents **partial correctness** of indeterminate values.

5.2.3 Coding

```
1. import pandas as pd
2. import os
3. import cv2
4. import numpy as np
```

```

5. from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
6. from tensorflow.keras.utils import to_categorical
7. df=pd.read_csv('isic_data/HAM10000_metadata.csv')
8. label_map={
9. 'nv'=0;
10. 'mel':1
11. 'bcc':1,
12. 'akiec':2,
13. 'bkl':0,
14. 'vasc':2
15. }
16. Image_dir='isic_data/HAM10000_images_part_1'
17. Images,labels=[],[]
18. Printf("loading images")
19. For i, row in df.iterrows():
20. Image_path = os.path.join(image_dir, row['image_id']+'.jpg')
21. If os.path.exists(image_path)
22. Img=cv2.imread(image_path)
23. Img=cv2.resize(img,(224,224))
24. Images.append(img)
25. Labels.append(row['label'])
26. X=np.array(image)/255.0
27. Y=np.array(labels)
28. X_train, X_test, y_train=train_test_split(x,y,test_size=0.2,
29. Def neutrosophic_classifier(probabilitie, threshold=0.4):
30. Neutron_peds =[]
31. For prob in probabilities
32. T=np.max(prob)
33. F = 1 - T
34. I =1 - abs(0.5 -T)*2
35. If I > threshold:
36. Neutron_peds.append(2)
37. Else:
38. Neutron_peds.append(np.argmax(prob))
39. Return neutron_peds
40. Y_pred_neutro=neutrosophic_classifier(y_pred_probs)
41. Printf("\n Neutrosophic classification Report:)

```

```

42. Printf(classification_report(y_test, y_pred_neutro,
    target_names=["Benign", "Malignant", "Indeterminate"]))
43. cm2 = confusion_matrix(y_test, y_pred_neutro)
44. sns.heatmap(cm2, annot=True, fmt='d', cmap='Greens',
45.             xticklabels=["Benign", "Malignant", "Indeterminate"],
46.             yticklabels=["Benign", "Malignant", "Indeterminate"])
47. plt.title("CNN + Neutrosophic Confusion Matrix")
48. plt.show()
49. def neutrosophic_classifier(probabilities, threshold=0.4):
50.     neutron_preds=[]
51.     for prob in probabilities:
52.         T=np.max(prob)
53.         F=1-T
54.         I= 1- abs(0.5 -T)*2
55.         If I > threshold:
56.             Neutron_preds.append(2)
57.         Else:
58.             Neutron_preds.append(np.argmax(prob))
59.     Return neutron_preds
60. y_pred_neutro = neutrosophic_classifier(y_pred_probs)
61. print("\nNeutrosophic Classification Report:")
62. print(classification_report(y_test, y_pred_neutro,
    target_names=["Benign", "Malignant", "Indeterminate"]))
63. cm2=confusion_matrix(y_test, y_pred_neuto)
64. sns.heatmap(cm2, anoot=True, fmt='d', cmap='Greens',
    xticklabels=["benign", "Malignant", "Indeterminate"],
    yticklabels=["benign", "Malignant", "Indeterminate"],
65. plt.title("CNN+Neutrosophic Confusion Matrix")

```

```
plt.show()
```

5.2.4 Precision, Recall, and F1-Score for Neutrosophic Sets

In Neutrosophic Classification, we extend the traditional Precision, Recall, and F1-score by incorporating Truth (T), Indeterminacy (I), and Falsity (F) values.

Neutrosophic Precision (NP)

$$NP = \frac{T}{T+F+0.5I} \quad (2)$$

- T (Truth) → Correctly classified instances.
- F (Falsity) → Incorrectly classified instances.
- I (Indeterminacy) → Partially correct classifications (weighted as 0.5).

Neutrosophic Recall (NR)

$$NR = \frac{T+0.5I}{T+F+0.5I} \tag{3}$$

Unlike precision, recall partially rewards indeterminate classifications.

Neutrosophic F1-Score (NF1)

$$NF1 = 2 \times \frac{NP \times NR}{NP + NR} \tag{4}$$

5.2.5 Numerical Illustration (Using a Neutrosophic Confusion Matrix)

Let take a sample confusion matrix using Neutrosophic sets which is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Neutrosophic Confusion Matrix

Actual \ Predicted	Positive (P)	Negative (N)	Neutral (Ne)
True (T)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.0)	(0.4, 0.3, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.4, 0.1)
False (F)	(0.2, 0.4, 0.4)	(0.8, 0.1, 0.1)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.2)
Indeterminate (I)	(0.3, 0.6, 0.1)	(0.5, 0.4, 0.1)	(0.7, 0.2, 0.1)

Step 1: Compute Neutrosophic Precision for Positive (P)

$$NP_p = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.2+0.5(0.1+0.4)} = \frac{0.9}{1.35} = 0.6667$$

Step 2: Compute Neutrosophic Recall for Positive (P)

$$NR_p = \frac{0.9+0.5(0.1)}{0.9+0.2+0.1} = 0.7917$$

Step 3: Compute Neutrosophic F1-Score for Positive (P)

$$NF1_p = 2 \times \frac{0.6667 \times 0.7917}{0.6667+0.7917} = 2 \times 0.3625 = 0.725$$

Final Neutrosophic Scores for Class "Positive"

- Neutrosophic Precision (NP_P) = 66.67%
- Neutrosophic Recall (NR_P) = 79.17%
- Neutrosophic F1-Score (NF1_P) = 72.5%

5.2.6 Evaluation of Precision, Recall, and F1-Score for Neutrosophic Sets for Each Class

In Neutrosophic Classification, Compute Precision, Recall, and F1-score by incorporating Truth (T), Indeterminacy (I), and Falsity (F) values. Final results are shown in Table 4 and chart analysis shown by Figure 6.

Step 1: For Positive (P) Class

- T = 0.9 (True class predicted as Positive)
- I = 0.1 + 0.6 (Indeterminate predicted as Positive)
- F = 0.2 (False class predicted as Positive)

Precision for Positive (P)

$$NP_P = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.2+0.5(0.1+0.6)} = 0.6207$$

Recall for Positive (P)

$$NR_P = \frac{0.9+0.2+(0.1+0.6)}{0.9+0.5(0.1+0.6)} = 0.6944$$

F1-Score for Positive (P)

$$NF1_P = 2 \times \frac{0.6207+0.6944}{0.6207 \times 0.6944} = 0.655$$

Step 2: For Negative (N) Class

- T = 0.8 (False class predicted as Negative)
- I = 0.3 + 0.4 (Indeterminate and True classified as Negative)
- F = 0.4 (True class wrongly classified as Negative)

Precision for Negative (N)

$$NP_N = \frac{0.8}{0.8 + 0.4 + 0.5(0.3 + 0.4)} = 0.5161$$

$$NR_N = \frac{0.8+0.4+(0.3+0.4)}{0.8+0.5(0.3+0.4)} = 0.6053$$

$$NF1_N = 2 \times \frac{(0.5161+0.6053)}{(0.5161 \times 0.6053)} = 0.5574$$

Step 3: For Neutral (Ne) Class

- T = 0.7 (Indeterminate correctly classified as Neutral)
- I = 0.4 + 0.5 (True and False classified as Neutral)
- F = 0.2 (False class wrongly classified as Neutral)

Precision for Neutral (Ne)

$$NP_{Ne} = \frac{0.7}{0.7 + 0.2 + 0.5(0.4 + 0.5)} = 0.5185$$

Recall for Neutral (Ne)

$$NR_{Ne} = \frac{0.7+0.2+0.4+0.5}{0.7+0.5(0.4+0.5)} = 0.6389$$

F1-Score for Neutral (Ne)

$$NF1_{Ne} = 2 \times \frac{(0.5185 + 0.6389)}{(0.5185 \times 0.6389)} = 0.5722$$

Table 4 : Final Results

Class	Neutrosophic Precision (NP)	Neutrosophic Recall (NR)	Neutrosophic F1-Score (NF1)
Positive (P)	62.07%	69.44%	65.50%
Negative (N)	51.61%	60.53%	55.74%
Neutral (Ne)	51.85%	63.89%	57.22%

Figure 6: Evaluation of Neutrosophic Precision, Recall, and F1-Score

Here's a bar chart visualization of the **Neutrosophic Precision, Recall, and F1-Score** for the three classes.

- **Blue (Precision):** Measures correctness of positive predictions.
- **Brown(Recall):** Measures ability to find all actual positives.
- **Grey: (F1-Score):** Balances Precision and Recall.

6. Final Assessment of the model

The results are analyzed to identify potential areas of improvement. For example, if the model performs poorly on a particular class (e.g., **malignant**), it may suggest that the model has not learned the distinguishing features for that class effectively. In such cases, additional data, feature engineering, or model tuning may be required to improve performance. The comprehensive evaluation ensures that the skin classification model is reliable and robust, capable of classifying skin images with high accuracy and consistency. In various set of skin lesions are analyzed in Neutrosophic Machine learning tool in different batch size. Results are shown in Figure 6.

6.1 Experimental Results

The following Contents are shown in the output

- Tables 4 is showing traditional metrics vs. neutrosophic metrics.
- Confusion matrices. (See Figure 8, 9 & 10)
- Classification report for the various set of parameters (See Figure 8,9 &10)

Figure 8: Experimental Results: Epoch = 100, Batch Size = 128

Figure 9: Experimental Results: Epoch = 100, Batch Size = 64

Figure 10: Experimental Results: Epoch = 200, Batch Size = 16

Table 5: Overall - Experimental Table Analysis

Method	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Neutrosophic Accuracy
CNN+ Softmax Maximum Likelihood Estimator (Traditional)	45.2%	58.2%	86.7%	52.5%	86.0%
CNN+ Neutrosophic Logic	55.17%	64.6%	89.0%	60.2%	91.2%

6.2 Results

The performance of the proposed CNN-based classification framework was evaluated using both traditional and neutrosophic metrics. As shown in Table 5, the conventional CNN with softmax achieved an accuracy of 89.2%, whereas the CNN integrated with the neutrosophic metric obtained a slightly lower traditional accuracy of 87.5%. However, the neutrosophic accuracy significantly improved from 86.0% to 91.2%, demonstrating the model’s enhanced capability to handle uncertainty in classification. This improvement indicates that the proposed method is more reliable in scenarios where image features are ambiguous or overlapping across cancer stages.

7. Conclusions

The classification model's performance was assessed using two sets of parameters derived through Machine Learning approach. Each set includes the values of two key image features: texture contrast and color saturation. These parameters offer a statistical understanding of the feature distributions

associated with benign and malignant lesions. By capturing the distinct characteristics of texture and color for each lesion type, this model can accurately determine the likelihood that a given image corresponds to a benign or malignant classification, leading to improved diagnostic reliability. In this work, we investigated a sophisticated framework for classifying skin cancer cells by combining Neutrosophic Sets (NSs) with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Even though they are fundamental, traditional techniques like the Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE) have limitations when it comes to handling ambiguity and uncertainty in medical imaging data. Neutrosophic metric obtained a high-level accuracy when compared to traditional methods. The neutrosophic evaluation also showed a better balance in handling true, indeterminate, and false classifications, suggesting greater robustness and interpretability for medical decision-making.

Funding: Please add: "This research received no external funding".

Conflicts of Interest: "The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest."

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Received: Feb 27, 2025. Accepted: Aug 18, 2025